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Myths, Monsters, Maidens

Jason's Archetypal Quest for the Golden Fleece

By

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In the BBC World documentary Ancient Greek Heroes: Myth and Modern Vision (Bragard, 2004), the mythical hero Jason is presented as a highly admirable role model. Not only does he overcome a fire-breathing dragon and obtain the legendary Golden Fleece, but the documentary also suggests that his journey provides him with profound insights into life in general and the opposite sex in particular. However, this optimistic portrayal of Jason's character and achievements scarcely aligns with the depiction found in ancient Greek sources. With the help of Jungian psychology, we uncover an unexpected subtext in the original narrative while simultaneously highlighting the continuing relevance of this archetypal quest for our own time.

I—Myth and Truth

Although the tale of Jason and the Golden Fleece is widely known and even iconic, it is difficult to fathom. First and foremost, we are not dealing with a literary work authored by a single individual, but with a myth—a narrative with no identifiable origin, shaped over generations by countless anonymous storytellers before it found its way into written sources.

The story of Jason appears to date back exceptionally far, even by the standards of Greek mythology. It was widely disseminated throughout the ancient Greek world, and a rich oral tradition about this mythological subject must have existed long before the classical era. For instance, Homer (8th–7th century BCE) makes several casual references to Jason’s adventurous expedition,¹ as does Hesiod (7th century BCE).² Both authors seem to assume that their audience is already familiar with the details, which could only be the case if this mythological material had long been an integral part of early Greek culture. Also the prominent role that the archaic city-state of Iolkos—flourishing in the second millennium BCE—plays within the narrative suggests considerable antiquity. And not only do the roots of the Jason myth run deep, but it also retained its popularity throughout all later periods of Greek Antiquity.

Another notable aspect of the Jason myth is the absence of a fully standardized version. While many people have a fairly clear image of the adventures of Odysseus, thanks to the significant influence of Homer’s *Odyssey*, which eclipses all alternative traditions, the tale of Jason’s quest is far less uniform. It has reached us through a diverse array of sources, each typically covering only a part of the journey and often differing significantly in detail. Among the extant texts, Euripides’ tragedy *Medea* (431 BCE) is the most well-known, but this version is rather incomplete. Although it incorporates flashbacks to some of the earlier events, it mainly focuses on the conclusion of the story cycle, following Medea’s vengeful wrath after Jason abandons her for another woman.

Nevertheless, the core narrative remains sufficiently clear, partly thanks to three comprehensive works from Late Antiquity that retrospectively arranged the key facts for posterity.³ While the literary quality of these compilations is limited,

¹ Homer, *Odyssey* XII 69–72 and *Iliad* VII 467–475. Additionally, Homer mentions the ancestry of several members of Jason’s family in *Odyssey* XI 235–259.

² Hesiod, *Theogony* 956–962 and 993–1002.

³ The *Bibliotheca Historica* of Diodorus Siculus (1st century BCE), the *Fabulae* of Hyginus (1st/2nd century CE), and the *Bibliotheca* attributed to (Pseudo-)Apollodorus (1st/2nd century CE).

they are valuable for their contribution to reconstructing the major mythological cycles of ancient Greek tradition, including the intricate tale surrounding the retrieval of the Golden Fleece.

The rich imagery and psychological depth of such myths have long intrigued scholars. Carl Gustav Jung, for one, regards them as significant sources of insight into unconscious processes and behavioral patterns. In his view, myths are comparable to the dreams of individuals, but unlike the latter, they carry a significance that extends beyond the personal, resonating within the collective and cultural sphere. In other words, he sees them as the *via regia* to the collective unconscious.⁴ (To be sure, Jung refers to authentic myths integral to pre-modern cultures, not politicized fabrications disseminated as fake news with propagandistic intent.) Interestingly, in Antiquity, Jason's quest was thought of as a Panhellenic undertaking, with nearly all the prominent heroes of Greek mythology eagerly joining him in his daring mission to retrieve the Golden Fleece from Colchis. It is no coincidence that Homer refers to the voyage of the Argo as being of universal importance.⁵ From a Jungian perspective, the widespread sense of involvement in Jason's adventure within Greek culture suggests that we are not dealing with a mere invention by any one individual, but rather with a genuine archetypal quest narrative—one that is rooted in the collective unconscious.

Given the unique nature of myths, Jung cautions against approaching them with misplaced rationality. In his view, myths are not cleverly crafted allegories of known truths, let alone messages about agricultural or meteorological phenomena disguised as spirituality.⁶ On the contrary, they represent a spontaneous,

Although Diodorus is a historian rather than a mythographer, this distinction matters little when assessing the 'bare facts' of Jason's journey, which he appears to regard as a historical event. The other two focus on systematically cataloging the mythological cycles known to them.

⁴ See, e.g., Jung 1916/1981, paras. 108–109; 1952/1981, para. 611; 1954/1985, paras. 261–264.

⁵ *Odyssey* XII 70: Ἀργὸν πᾶσι μέλουσα [the Argo, who is everyone's concern].

⁶ See, e.g., Jung 1920/1981, para. 322. The eminent classicist Geoffrey S. Kirk also emphasizes the unique nature of myths, warning against narrowing them down or misinterpreting them as primitive early attempts at scientific inquiry—a mistake that, in his view, is frequently made (Kirk,

unconscious engagement with profound existential questions within the culture in which they circulated. Therefore, he argues, they should be understood *symbolically* rather than as straightforward contributions to historical or other forms of knowledge.⁷

Myths, then, are not meant to convey truth in any conventional sense of the term; their value lies elsewhere. Rather than offering logically and/or empirically testable truths, myths are concerned with meaning.⁸

It is this meaningfulness that helps us (re)connect with our inner selves. Like works of art—it is not just myths at play; religion, and certainly the arts, reside in the same domain of meaningfulness—⁹ myths have the remarkable power to shift our focus from life’s inevitable trivialities and bring us back to our core. They offer a symbolic reflection on essential matters—issues that resonate in the light of eternity.¹⁰ Thus, Jung argues, myths have a compensatory function. They

1974/1990, pp. 53–54).

⁷ See, e.g., Jung 1952/1981, paras. 4–46 (= Über die zwei Arten des Denkens. GW 5, pp. 25–54).

⁸ In Kardaun 2010 and 2015, I explore the difference between what is ‘true’ and what is ‘meaningful’ in more detail, offering several examples from mythology and literature. In more theoretical language and far greater detail, the Dutch philosopher L. M. de Rijk distinguishes between a ‘domain of truth’ and a ‘domain of meaningfulness.’ In his view, both are equally important, yet each serves distinct objectives and follows its own set of rules. Unfortunately, this distinction often goes unnoticed, and when the two realms are naively conflated, undesirable consequences can arise (De Rijk 2008, pp. 127–130 and 171–203; De Rijk 2010, pp. 134–147). Jung’s concept of the “zwei Arten des Denkens” reflects the same crucial distinction. It is, however, regrettable that Jung speaks of “two kinds of thinking”—or sometimes “two kinds of truth”—when it would have been more apt to speak of ‘truth’ and ‘meaning.’ This may, however, be primarily a matter of terminology.

⁹ Walter Schönau aptly illustrates, with examples, how literary works may possess an enthralling intensity that fulfills our need for meaning and purpose in today’s disenchanted world (Schönau 1991).

¹⁰ ‘Eternity,’ of course, must be taken *cum grano salis*. In Jung’s own words: “Während wir in Zeitläuften von Jahren denken, denkt und lebt das Unbewußte aber in Zeitläuften von Jahrtausenden” [While we think in epochs of years, the unconscious thinks and lives in epochs of

compensate the inherent limitations of human consciousness, which tends to be ensnared in a labyrinth of short-term concerns and strategies. These demands consume so much of our attention that we easily lose sight of the larger frameworks. Mythical narratives address this imbalance by offering us glimpses of a cohesive and meaningful whole that tends to fill us with a sense of purpose.¹¹

A similarly passionate critique of rationalistic and reductionist approaches to myths appears in a celebrated essay by writer and mythology scholar J.R.R. Tolkien.¹² Much like Jung, Tolkien does not regard the fantastical and fabulous content of mythical stories as evidence of a lack of understanding on the part of their ancient storytellers, as if the latter were somehow unable to distinguish between inner and outer realities. Nor does he seek to reduce the fantastical elements of myths to a mere display of rhetorical brilliance, as if the authors were simply indulging in extravagant metaphors that amount to nothing more than colorful descriptions of mundane events. For Tolkien, the strange supernatural beings and occurrences found in mythology are precisely what these stories are about; they represent the most fitting expression of something that resists rational articulation but whose significance is nonetheless deeply felt. Therefore, the supernatural elements of myths should not be ignored or explained away but deserve our full attention.

millennia] (Jung 1954/1985 para. 499). Cf. the *sophisme de l'éphémère* [fallacy of the ephemeral], coined by Denis Diderot in *Le rêve de D'Alembert*, where he has Mademoiselle de L'Espinasse declare that “de mémoire de rose on n'avait vu mourir un jardinier” [in the memory of a rose, no gardener has been seen to die] (Diderot & Assézat 1769/1875] p. 134).

¹¹ See e.g. Jung 1952/1981 para. 655; Jung 1954/1985 paras. 456–458; Jung 1930/1984 paras. 152–153.

¹² Tolkien 1936/2006. Somewhere else—I regret I cannot recall where—Tolkien remarks that he had two grievances with Mr. Hitler. The first was general: the Nazi leader was a totalitarian and an enemy of England. The second was personal: through his deliberate perversion of mythic heritage, Hitler had discredited the entire field of mythology.

II—Jason’s Expedition to the Mysterious land of Colchis

With these warnings and exhortations in mind, let us examine how the educational BBC World documentary *Ancient Greek Heroes: Myth and Modern Vision*¹³ presents the myth of Jason. The filmmakers tackle their subject with admirable cheerfulness and seem determined to extract a happy ending at all costs. Their central thesis is that the myth revolves around a (relatively) modern hero—one distinguished more by intellect than physical strength—who, in their view, served as a more appealing role model for the youth of Antiquity than the older hero Heracles, who also features in the myth. Jason, they argue, undergoes a series of rites of passage on his journey to manhood. He is portrayed as a human, doubting hero who nevertheless succeeds brilliantly. Not only does he prove himself by obtaining the Golden Fleece, but he also gains many valuable life lessons throughout his journey. In particular, they suggest, he comes to understand women.

However, the story features scarcely any women. There are goddesses, she-monsters, unredeemed feminine beasts, and witches, but that is not the same thing—and what is more, he does not come to understand even them. If there is one striking element of the Jason myth, it is the hero’s persistent inability—or even outright refusal—to grasp anything resembling a feminine perspective. Like so many other heroes in Greek mythology, Jason suffers from *hybris*, meaning overconfidence and self-delusion. Greek myths rarely come with a happy ending,¹⁴ and Jason’s story is no exception. As we will see, it ends in catastrophic failure, brought on by his breathtaking naivety, smug complacency, and silly projections shaped by gender biases.

The story begins promisingly enough with a birth—befitting heroes and heroines—surrounded by miracles and omens. Jason is the son of the rightful king of the city-state

¹³ Bragard 2004.

¹⁴ As Herbert Golder so eloquently states, the Greek hero “has come into this world for one purpose and one purpose alone: and that is to destroy himself. . . . While the heroes of every culture expand the parameters of what is believed to be possible, the Greek hero does so while at the same time reminding us of our human-all-too-human fate, reminding us, that is, of what it means to be human, the upper reaches but also the lower depths. And this is what makes the Greek hero’s ability to snatch the eternal from the desperately fleeting that much more remarkable.” (Golder 2012, p. 5)

of Iolkos. As an infant, he narrowly escapes an assassination attempt, orchestrated by a malevolent usurper by the name of Pelias, who has seized the throne by force and, heeding a foreboding oracle, takes the precaution of killing all the boys in his vicinity. Through a clever ruse, Jason is spirited to safety, and his upbringing is entrusted to a centaur.

And Pelias receives yet another oracle: he should beware of a man with only one sandal. When Jason returns to his hometown as a young adult to claim his rightful position, he must cross a river. An inconspicuous old woman asks for his help to reach the other side, and Jason offers to carry her. However, he soon discovers that she is a heavy burden. The old woman is, in fact, the mother goddess Hera. She has been neglected in Iolkos lately, as the tyrannical king Pelias chooses to honor only the father god Poseidon—a highly unusual stance in the polytheistic Greek context. In the struggle to bring the goddess across the river, one of Jason’s sandals gets stuck in the mud, and he arrives in Iolkos wearing only one sandal. Pelias looks at Jason’s feet and asks, “What would you do if you had received an oracle about someone that he posed a threat to your life?” Jason replies, “I would send him to retrieve the Golden Fleece.” Pelias responds, “Very well. Go then, and bring me the Golden Fleece.”¹⁵

The task resting on Jason’s shoulders is decidedly ambitious. The Fleece is located in the distant land of Colchis, the realm of the powerful King Aeëtes (modern-day Georgia). Aeëtes is the son of the sun god Helios and a brother of the sorceress Circe. Not only is Colchis far away, almost as if in another world, but the Fleece is also guarded by a gigantic dragon that never sleeps. However, Jason remains undeterred. He builds a ship, the famous Argo [‘the swift one’], and persuades approximately fifty other heroes—including Heracles, Theseus, and Orpheus—to join him on his quest. Thus begins the legendary adventure of the Argonauts.

The first stop is Lemnos, an island inhabited exclusively by women. These women, in desperate need of offspring, greet the Argonauts with wine, food, and seductive charm. Jason and his men are pleasantly surprised by the remarkably warm welcome, but their enticing hostesses harbor a deadly secret—they are ruthless murderesses. Pindar refers to them as “the tribe of man-slaying women.”¹⁶ The mission is salvaged by Heracles, who

¹⁵ Apollodorus, *Bibliotheca* 1.9.16 and Hyginus, *Fabulae* XII (slightly paraphrased).

¹⁶ Pindar, *Pythian Ode* IV 252.

seizes Jason by the neck and hurls him back onto the Argo. According to the documentary, these experiences serve as an invaluable first lesson for the Argonauts. After all, “if they’re going to be men, they’ve got to know what sex is.”¹⁷

Several episodes later, the encounter with the women of Lemnos still reverberates. In the meantime, the Argonauts have accidentally killed a befriended king, abandoned Heracles somewhere along the way, disposed of a number of screeching Harpies (female, hybrid, bird-like creatures whose well-aimed excrement renders human food inedible), and, with Hera’s assistance, managed to sail through the infamous Clashing Rocks with only minimal damage. Although the crew is now suffering from hunger and the ship is in dire need of fresh supplies, Jason chooses to bypass the territory of the man-hating Amazons, a fierce tribe of female warriors. The documentary makers applaud this decision, describing it as prudent. And indeed, ‘prudence’ is precisely what they assert we should learn from the hero’s discreetly slipping past the Amazon region (it is their lesson number 6).

Later still, the Argonauts face the threat of falling victim to the Sirens.¹⁸ Sirens are particularly nasty creatures, half-woman and half-bird, who lure sailors to their doom by singing irresistibly beautiful songs, causing ships to crash on the rocks. Fortunately, the legendary singer Orpheus comes to the rescue, drowning out the hypnotic melodies of these “simply very, very, very sexy women, who are also killers”¹⁹ with his own superior music. In the episode with the Sirens, the documentary filmmakers discern not one but two lessons on “how to be a man”: lesson 7, they suggest, is that a young leader must sometimes accept the help of others, while via lesson 8, “Greek men are being cautioned that there are some dangerous women out there.”²⁰

Finally, the Argonauts arrive at their destination: the court of King Aeëtes of Colchis.

¹⁷ Bragard 2004.

¹⁸ Although the confrontation with the Sirens, according to all original sources, occurs only when the Argonauts are on their return journey with the Fleece, the documentary makers have chosen to depict this event as taking place during the outward journey. They may have wished to deal with all the other female fantasy figures before focusing on Jason’s encounter with the sorceress Medea.

¹⁹ Bragard 2004.

²⁰ Bragard 2004.

Jason has no elaborate plan and simply asks Aeëtes for the Fleece. Through an oracle, Aeëtes is aware that the loss of this magical object will mark the end of his reign. He responds that Jason may have the Fleece if he manages to single-handedly yoke two enormous, fire-breathing bulls with bronze hooves. Should he succeed, he must then plow a field with these beasts and sow dragon's teeth (although Aeëtes does not reveal what this will ultimately lead to). And, still lurking in the background is, of course, the ever-present and terrifying guardian of the Fleece—the dragon that never sleeps.

Jason himself is not up to any of these tasks and threats. Luckily, however, the king has a daughter, Medea, who has magical powers and falls head over heels for Jason. She provides him with crucial information about the fire-breathing bulls and explains what he must do after sowing the dragon's teeth (from which armed warriors will spring). On top of this, she supplies him with a range of magical remedies. Medea takes care of everything—Jason need only follow her instructions. She has but one condition: he must marry her and take her to Greece. Jason swears a solemn oath to this effect,²¹ and everything proceeds as planned: the bulls are yoked, the armed warriors are swiftly dealt with, and the dragon is subdued with one of Medea's potions (depending on the source, the creature is either killed or put to sleep.) They seize the Fleece—according to Apollodorus,²² it is once again Medea, not Jason, who accomplishes this—and, under the cover of night, they weigh anchor and flee Colchis.

A furious King Aeëtes immediately sets off in pursuit. Medea has anticipated this as well, and has brought along her younger brother Apsyrtos. She cuts him into pieces and periodically throws parts of his body into the sea. The time it takes for Aeëtes to collect the scattered remains causes him to fall behind. Thus, the couple escapes to Iolkos. According to the filmmakers, the way in which Jason escapes with the Fleece serves as “a gentle reminder to the young men of ancient Greece that while the fairer sex may lead them astray, they won't get far without a good woman,”²³ and with this somewhat astonishing lesson (lesson 9), the documentary concludes.

However, the original myth is now only halfway through. After the couple has arrived in Iolkos, Medea, eager to please her beloved, kills the usurper-king Pelias. She does so in

²¹ Apollonius Rhodius, *Argonautica* IV, 93-99; Euripides, *Medea* 20-23.

²² Apollodorus, *Bibliotheca* 1.9.23.

²³ Bragard 2004.

an exceedingly cunning manner, and of course, with the help of her magical arsenal. She claims she wants to perform a rejuvenation treatment on Pelias. By way of demonstration, she chops a ram into pieces in front of his daughters. Adding a special potion, she cooks the animal in a cauldron, and lo and behold, a fresh little lamb leaps out! The daughters are thrilled, overpower their father, and hack him into pieces. Expectantly, they look to Medea for the next steps, but she merely laughs and takes no further action.

Medea is ruthless and capable of anything. She has little hesitation when it comes to committing murder, and as a sorceress and the granddaughter of Helios she has an almost infinite number of artful tricks and strategies at her disposal. Consumed by her love for Jason, she is willing to go to any lengths for him, even to the extent of chopping her own brother into little bits. Her actions not only reveal the depth of her madness but also her irreversible decision to spend the rest of her life with Jason. (In ancient Greece, brothers were generally considered a safety net for women whose marriages might fail.) Given all this, most people would likely find Medea rather scary. Some degree of caution in dealing with her would certainly not go amiss. Jason, however, is not cautious at all; he seems to find it convenient to have such a resourceful girlfriend. In ancient Greek culture, a poor judgment like that of Jason is a clear sign of *hybris*.

The murder of Pelias turns Jason and Medea into fugitives. Like an ancient Bonnie and Clyde, the couple is now on the run across Greece. In the city of Corinth, Jason decides it is time to advance his position. To marry the daughter of King Creon and become the intended successor to the throne, he casts Medea aside, telling her she must leave him. Her initial response is frantic rage, but then, with sudden composure and politeness, she requests a one-day delay before her departure, claiming there are matters she must attend to. She then proceeds to kill both Jason's new fiancée and his future father-in-law, and ultimately even murders her own children—the two sons she had with Jason. Thereupon she escapes, soaring through the air in a sun-chariot drawn by winged dragons.

As for Jason's end, the ancient sources vary, but none of the versions are pleasant. Our hero meets his death in a fire set by Medea,²⁴ or he takes his own life after being aban-

²⁴ Hyginus, *Fabulae* XXV.

doned by everyone,²⁵ or his skull is cleaved by a loose fragment of the decaying Argo.²⁶ The latter image is particularly striking: he literally perishes due to his earlier formula for success. Perhaps the fabulous ship was a little too swift after all. The actions Jason takes are devoid of true understanding and lasting results. Therefore, there is no happy ending, and they do not live happily ever after.

III—Cherchez la Femme

There is no doubt that gender dynamics play a significant role in Jason's quest for the Golden Fleece. However, contrary to what the filmmakers seem to assume, this is not a matter of women whom the hero might encounter, but rather of images of the feminine that emerge successively throughout the story. These images are far from uplifting; they are unresolved, primitive, and problematic.

The difficulties begin with an unlawful and godless king who maintains a tight grip on the city-state of Iolkos.²⁷ In order to secure his position of power, the wretch Pelias does not hesitate to commit infanticide. He also grossly insults the mother goddess Hera (by murdering supplicants, no less, at her altar) and suppresses her worship.²⁸ Meanwhile, the legitimate heir to the throne, the hero of our tale, is being raised deep in the forests by the centaur Cheiron.²⁹ From a Jungian perspective, this could suggest that in the unconscious a correction to the situation is being prepared—namely, a new mindset that will, hopefully, be more in harmony with the wisdom of nature.

Once he has reached adulthood, the hero returns to Iolkos. On his journey, he helps an old lady across a river. The lady is, in fact, Hera in disguise, meaning that it is the mother goddess herself whom he brings along. This is likely the reason why he is named Jason.

²⁵ Diodorus Siculus, *Bibliotheca Historica* IV 55.

²⁶ Euripides, *Medea* 1386–1389. Apollonius Rhodius also hints at an unfortunate outcome, but without providing details (*Argonautica* IV, 32–65).

²⁷ Pindar, *Pythian Ode* IV 106–116. Hesiod characterizes Pelias not only as arrogant and violent but also explicitly as ὕβριστής, meaning someone who does not respect the divine laws (*Theogony* 996).

²⁸ Apollodorus, *Bibliotheca* 1.9.8 and 1.9.16; Apollonius Rhodius, *Argonautica* I, 14.

²⁹ Unlike the average, more libidinous centaur, Cheiron is consistently described as wise. He is the perfect educator of great heroes. Pindar calls him a divine animal (*Pythian Ode* IV 119).

The name 'Jason' is etymologically related to the verb ἰάσθαι ['to heal'] and can be translated as 'Healer' or perhaps 'Savior.' Given that his birthplace is entirely under the dominion of paternal authority, this reintroduction of lost maternal values signifies nothing less than a restoration of balance. It is Jason's first heroic deed. However, it is important to recognize that he performs this act without conscious intent or calculation; he is simply a nice young man being kind when an elderly lady asks for his help. Nonetheless, from this point on, he becomes Hera's special favorite. She will assist him wherever she can.

Due to the effort required to get Hera to the right side of the river, Jason arrives in Iolkos with only one sandal on his feet. This peculiar detail, which appears in nearly all the sources, may symbolize that he occupies—or at least can occupy—two perspectives simultaneously: with his shod foot, he stands within the realm of civilized human interaction, while with his other foot, he is in direct contact with the earth, uncultivated, unpretentious, and spontaneous. He embodies both culture and nature within his person. The hero's holistic orientation is important because it compensates for the one-sided, brutal law-and-order mentality that prevails in Iolkos.

In summary, if anyone can be considered capable of successfully completing a significant second task after this initial triumph, it is the young hero Jason.

The second task is as follows: not only is there a lack of maternal values in the Greek world, but Greek society as a whole is also in need of revitalization. Several generations ago, the Greeks lost the Golden Fleece, a loss brought about by insolence, deceit, and negligence. An inattentive king (Jason's great-uncle) and a scheming, wicked stepmother acted in such a way that the two children of the rightful queen were forced to flee. The pair escaped on a golden ram that could fly effortlessly through the skies. The boy, named Phrixus ['Curlyhead'], managed, with the help of the extraordinary animal, to reach King Aeëtes in Colchis, but his sister fell into the sea along the way. Phrixus sacrificed the ram to Zeus and gave the precious fleece to Aeëtes as a gift. Since then, the Golden Fleece has hung in a sacred grove in Colchis, beyond the reach of Greek society, guarded by a massive dragon.

It is time for the Fleece to be retrieved and made available once again, for this powerful magical object is of the utmost importance. It can be compared to the Holy Grail and other symbols of the Self. More specifically, the Golden Fleece symbolizes a divine right

to rule,³⁰ or, in more modern terms, legitimate leadership—the kind of leadership that is undisputed because it honors all relevant interests and is neither selfish nor unfair.³¹ The legendary Fleece originates from and expresses—the animal side of it having been sacrificed—the spiritual ideal associated with the aforementioned golden ram. Animals symbolize (aspects of) our instinctual life, and a ram, as the leader of the flock, represents natural leadership and power. This particular specimen possesses flight and speech, is communicative, service-oriented, helpful, and, moreover, of a golden substance. ‘Gold’ signifies not only value and purity but also imperishability: “Gold corrupts, but does not corrode. Whether melted or reshaped, gold always remains itself.”³² Like sunlight, lightning,³³ and fire, gold can symbolize insight and, by extension, consciousness. In many myths and fairy tales, this special kind of gold must be retrieved from chthonic depths with great effort.³⁴ The lost Golden Fleece may symbolize a faded awareness of what a well-functioning, civilized society could look like. Deep within cultural memory, some notion of this beautiful and valuable ideal remains, and it would be of great benefit to the public good if this ideal were brought back to mind. Hence, for Jason to prove that he is indeed the one who deserves the throne, he must be able to present the Fleece.

The journey to the legendary Colchis, far beyond the known world, can be regarded as a descent into the unconscious. Colchis is a mysterious and dangerous place, full of darkness and unknown forces, more akin to the underworld than to the heavens. Getting there is challenging enough; escaping from it is nearly impossible.³⁵ According to Karl

³⁰ In related myths, such as those concerning the power struggle between the brothers Atreus and Thyestes, the narrative also revolves around a Golden Fleece: whoever succeeds in obtaining this object is deemed the one true king.

³¹ An interesting form of *Nachleben* of the Greek myth is found in the Order of the Golden Fleece, established by Philip the Good in 1430. Philip evidently had a keen sense of the symbolic meaning of the Fleece, as he explicitly associated it with divine election, just rule, and the highest ethical standards.

³² Welling 2024, p. 162.

³³ According to Apollonius Rhodius, the Fleece is “as radiant as the lightning of Zeus” (*Argonautica* IV, 185).

³⁴ Von Franz 1952/1986 volume I, pp. 381–383.

³⁵ In the earliest sources, the deadly collision of the Symplegades, the Clashing Rocks, occurs

Kerényi, Aeëtes, the king of Colchis, was both a son and a counterforce to Helios, and was originally scarcely distinguishable from the invisible and obscuring underworld god Hades.³⁶ The fact that Aeëtes' land lies in the east further reinforces his image as a ruler of the underworld; according to archaic Greek belief, the sun's rays, after disappearing in the west each day, must travel beneath the earth to emerge again in the east—a perilous journey each time.³⁷ No ancient source views the figure of Aeëtes in a positive light. He is consistently depicted as greedy, cruel, and deceitful. Homer describes him as one who is always filled with malicious intent.³⁸

In that ominous land, with its sinister king, the Golden Fleece is guarded by a gigantic dragon that never sleeps, capable of striking fatally at any moment—a frequent symbol of a regressive, chthonic force. At least within the context of Western³⁹ heroic myths, dragons and similar reptiles, such as serpents,⁴⁰ often represent ultra-conservative, and thus profoundly dangerous, tendencies. They can be seen as the dark side of the Great Mother. The latter, as is well known, can be endlessly benevolent, understanding, and warm, if she chooses to (and if she is treated well). She possesses the wisdom of the ages and always knows what to do, for she has witnessed it all before. However, she can also become suffocating if her protective nature leaves insufficient room for her offspring to develop themselves and become more conscious. At its worst, she manifests herself as a dragon, a cold-blooded instinctual reaction that seeks to smother any form of awareness at its inception, thus acting as an enemy of consciousness as such.⁴¹

only on the return journey from Colchis, suggesting that the realm resists departure. This aligns with Homer's assertion that the Argo, while fleeing from Aeëtes, was the only ship ever to pass these rocks. Even then, it could not have done so without Hera's intervention, who was driven by her love for Jason (*Odyssey* XII 69–72).

³⁶ Kerényi 1966/2003, p. 154 and Kerényi 1960/2002, p. 211.

³⁷ The poet Mimnermus (7th century BCE), for instance, speaks of “the city of Aeëtes, where the rays of the swift Sun are stored in a golden chamber” (Mimnermus, fragm. 11).

³⁸ Homer, *Odyssey* X 137.

³⁹ For the rich symbolism and diverse representations of serpents and dragons, particularly beyond established Western frameworks, see Welling 2012.

⁴⁰ In Antiquity, the distinction was not always clear; the Greek word δράκων signifies both ‘dragon’ and ‘serpent.’

⁴¹ See e.g. Jung 1909/1985, paras. 731–739 and Jung 1935/1981, paras. 190–201.

This imagery aligns perfectly with the beast encountered in Jason's myth. In Jungian terms, the purpose of the entire quest is, of course, to attain more consciousness, so that the development of the Self may have a chance. However, the necessary descent into the unconscious is fraught with risk. An *enantiodromia* (a reversal into its opposite) is always lurking around the corner. The little awareness that exists could very well be swallowed up in an instant. Yet this risk must be taken; reorganizing the psyche entails danger, but without risk, there can be no reward.

In summary: in times of moral collapse, the Golden Fleece—that lustrous ideal of harmony and fairness—disappeared into the unconscious. Now, it must be brought to light once more. Someone must set things right in the other world, so that the Greeks can move forward again, and that person is Jason. He has a positive mother complex, along with the accompanying self-confidence. He is not a rigid, grim figure like Pelias, who can only maintain his position through violence, nor is he a slavish devotee of rules. On the contrary, he is universally well-liked. He exudes a contagious enthusiasm and, with little effort, he manages to rally all of Greece to his cause; heroes from every corner of the land are drawn to him, eager to join in his grand and noble adventure. The quest itself seems to proceed smoothly: the many dangers along the way are overcome or, at times, quite literally bypassed, and the Fleece is eventually tracked down and wrested from the monstrous guardian.

However, Jason does not exactly slay the dragon himself. He is a *puer aeternus*,⁴² and in such a way that his flaws overshadow his initial virtues, resulting in serious consequences. This leads us to the final point: although Jason experiences many thrilling adventures and succeeds in carrying out his mission, the story ultimately does not have a happy ending. What sets the course for failure?

In Jungian terms, the quest for the Golden Fleece symbolizes a masculine individuation process. Naturally, this also involves an Anima figure; without the Anima (or Animus, for those identifying as female), self-realization cannot occur, for the Anima (or Animus) is an inseparable part of the Self. Jason must do more than merely feel comfortable with maternal values and, from there, engage in competition with a shadowy father figure. Successful individuation requires that, at a certain point, an Anima figure appears on

⁴² For a rich and insightful explanation of the concept of the *puer aeternus*, see Von Franz 1992 (in German) and 2000 (in English).

the scene and is then integrated into consciousness. To achieve a higher level of development, a figure is needed against whom the young hero must adopt an adult and responsible stance; otherwise, the ego will remain trapped in the childlike position of the son. Ideally, the myth's ultimate resolution would result in Iolkos receiving a wise new ruling couple after the previous ruler's despotism and one-sidedness, one that—armed with the ideals of the Golden Fleece and supported by the benevolence of both Poseidon and Hera—has the energy and ability to reshape society in a balanced and harmonious way.

And indeed, together with the Fleece, Jason brings something else back home: a young woman, the sorceress Medea. Other Anima figures appear throughout the quest as well: the offerings range from seductive murderesses to Harpies, Amazons, and Sirens, but these beings are all hostile, foreign, and threatening. Medea is different. Not only is she deeply in love with Jason, but she also possesses qualities that prove invaluable. For instance, she helps Jason resist the temptations of impulsive macho behavior.

Machismo is one of the potential side effects of an overly dominant role of the Great Mother. The typical macho man seeks to be ultra-masculine, strong, and independent, yet in reality, he tends to be ignorant of true masculine values. He is weak, vulnerable, and unfree, trapped in caricatured and stereotypical patterns of behavior (the kind of behavior that is labeled as 'toxic' today). Instead of wielding power consciously and intelligently, with valuable and attainable goals in mind, the macho man is drawn to just any fight. One of the tasks Jason must complete in order to have a chance at claiming the Fleece is sowing dragon's teeth. From these teeth, heavily armed, aggressive warriors emerge. Had he attempted to fight them, Jason would not have survived their attack. Fortunately, Medea knows what to do: she instructs Jason to throw a stone into their midst, for then these dim-witted brutes will attack each other instead of Jason. And so it happens.

Medea is sophisticated. She brings awareness and refinement. Moreover, she is indispensable in obtaining the Golden Fleece. However, a condition for all her help and cooperation is that, from now on, she must belong to Jason. Like all complexes, the Anima desires to be integrated into consciousness.

This, however, does not happen, or happens insufficiently. Jason, the special darling of mother goddess Hera, is a blissfully unconcerned mama's boy who fails to reach a higher

level of development. He is an astonishingly lazy hero who prefers to leave the work to others, starting with Hera herself. In fact, he is handed all the important matters of life on a silver platter, including the victory over the dragon, even though this was precisely the goal of his own quest! Most of his other achievements are also due to others; he enjoys teamwork and is happy to lean on his companions. When it comes to the opposite sex, he is even more passive. One could say that he behaves more like a sheep than a golden ram: Hera had to invite herself to Iolkos, and taking Medea home was not Jason's idea either. Essentially, he just follows along. That is a comfortable way of living, but prevents him from achieving a deeper understanding of the feminine, and hence of himself. In his relationship with the Anima, he behaves like a three-year-old. He seems to confuse Medea with just another mother figure. It never occurs to him that she might want anything other than merely to fulfill all his desires. Especially in Euripides' version, Jason exhibits such childlike self-importance and blindness that it is almost painful to read.⁴³ In short, the hero brings far too little awareness with him to integrate anything at all.

Moreover, this Anima figure might hardly be integrable to begin with. With an undifferentiated masculine ego comes a highly numinous unconscious feminine counterpart. Medea is not a human being but a wild sorceress devoid of any scruples. All the crimes she commits in order to be with Jason should make him reflect. He should take a stand against them, but he hardly seems bothered. Instead, he prefers to take advantage of her services. Rather than claiming the throne in Iolkos and working together toward a more decent society, the hero and his female counterpart engage in murder. As the story progresses, Jason starts looking quite a bit like Pelias, the evil force he once sought to defeat. He is no longer driven by enthusiasm, but by resentment, and seems directionless. He loses his sense of purpose—if he ever truly had one. Upon his return home, nothing worth mentioning is done with the Fleece, which, after all the effort, is at best disappointing. Jason loses his claim to the throne and ultimately loses everything.

In conclusion: to a certain extent, the archetypal hero Jason restores balance to the

⁴³ Euripides, *Medea* 446–626. It must have been painful to watch and hear for the audience of the time as well, for Euripides was notorious for his psychological hyperrealism as well as his depictions of female characters and unheroic males, which made him quite unpopular in his own era.

Greek value system, and that is admirable. Unfortunately, however, he is also a ‘sunny boy’ with an incurable mother complex and an unmanageable Anima. Therefore, after a promising start, this quest story remains unfinished.

The infortuitous outcome of the story broadly corresponds with the psycho-historical developments in Greek culture. The latter was characterized by a profound segregation between the sexes. Women had no presence in public life. Their viewpoints were neither seen nor discussed. Feminine perspectives remained off the radar, were underrepresented, did not enrich society, led their own obscure lives, and were, in the eyes of the Greek male, inappropriate, ridiculous, occasionally seen as otherworldly wise (as exemplified by the teachings of the figure of Diotima in Plato’s *Symposium*—almost certainly not a historical person, but a dramatic invention), but more often incomprehensible, irrational, and dangerous.

In my view, the Jason myth illustrates a fundamental problem of overly patriarchal cultures. Jason is by no means the only masculine epic hero who fails to benefit from the treasure he has acquired. The Athenian founder-hero Theseus, for example, completes a similar quest, but then abandons his helpful new girlfriend on an island, after which this heroic narrative, too, takes a negative turn. Similarly, St. George—the one from St. George and the Dragon—leaves the princess he has only recently saved behind just like that (the noble soul has better things to do, of course, namely to spread Christianity).⁴⁴ Many legendary heroes succeed in bringing the Anima up from the underworld or rescuing her from a dragon or other monster, but then do very little with this accomplishment. Accepting radical otherness as a valuable counterpart to oneself seems to pose a significant challenge, and as a result, the Self remains out of reach.

Of course, this fateful mechanism does not pertain so much to the behavior of individual men and women; rather, it reflects complex archetypal patterns and processes that have evolved over centuries. Even less does the Jason myth imply that the situation it depicts should remain unchanged—quite the opposite! In a recent book, the prominent scholar Carel van Schaik offers a highly insightful analysis of male–female relationships from historical, anthropological, and evolutionary-biological perspectives. He highlights how varying environmental demands and circumstances can give rise to vastly different societal structures. Van Schaik challenges common stereotypes by urging us to recon-

⁴⁴ Fordham University, n.d.

sider our assumptions about gender dynamics in light of these disciplines, ultimately underscoring the remarkable flexibility of human nature.⁴⁵ The renowned primatologist Frans de Waal adopts an even broader view in his (tragically final) book, comparing subtle differences in gender and sex among humans with those observed in our closest relatives in the animal kingdom. He emphasizes that, while his research reveals that gendered behavior is not shaped by cultural norms alone but also rooted in evolutionary biology and social dynamics, this does not automatically legitimize traditional gender roles. A deeper understanding of the background, complexity, and nuance of gender differences allows us to better assess which aspects of our social structures we might want—or need—to change.⁴⁶ These positions align with Jung’s response in an interview when asked which of Freud’s ideas he disagreed with: “Well, chiefly, his purely personal approach, and his disregard of the historical conditions of man. You see, we depend largely upon our history. We are shaped through education, through the influence of the parents, which is by no means always personal. They were prejudiced, or they were influenced by historical ideas or what are called dominants, and that is a most decisive factor in psychology. We are not of today or of yesterday; we are of an immense age.”⁴⁷

Unlike standard Hollywood productions, myths tend to be grounded in realism; they depict the world as it is rather than lulling us into complacency with saccharine illusions. This does not make myths depressing but rather truthful—and therefore beautiful. The quest for the holistic ideal of fairness and balance, as symbolized by the Golden Fleece, calls for a grounded sense of reality; wishful thinking will not do, nor will the mindless repetition or reinforcement of traditional gender roles. When we reflect on relatively recent societal phenomena—such as the LGBTQIA+ movement, along with manfluencers, tradwives, and incels—it raises the question of how far we have truly progressed in understanding both societal and personal expectations around gender. In our fragmented society, the need for greater consciousness remains as pressing as ever, and much work is still to be done.

⁴⁵ Van Schaik & Michel, 2020.

⁴⁶ De Waal, 2022.

⁴⁷ Jung 1959.

References:

- Bragard, J.-C. (Director). (2004). *Ancient Greek heroes: Myth and modern vision* [Film]. BBC Worldwide Americas, Inc.
- Diderot, D., & Assézat, J. (1875). *Oeuvres complètes de Diderot* (Vol. II). Garnier Frères. (Original work published 1769.)
- Fordham University. (n.d.). *The Golden Legend: Saint George*. Internet History Sourcebooks Project. <https://sourcebooks.fordham.edu/basis/goldenlegend/GL-vol3-george.asp>
- Franz, M.-L. von. (1986). *Symbolik des Märchens: Versuch einer Deutung* (3 vols.). A. Francke. (Original work published 1952–1957)
- Franz, M.-L. von. (1992). *Der ewige Jüngling*. Kösel.
- Franz, M.-L. von. (2000). *The problem of the puer aeternus*. Inner City Books.
- Golder, H. (2012). Unmodern observations. *Arion: A Journal of Humanities and the Classics*, 20(2), pp. 1–12.
- Jung, C. G. (1985). Die Bedeutung des Vaters für das Schicksal des Einzelnen. In *Gesammelte Werke* (Vol. 4, pp. 345–370). Walter-Verlag. (Original work published 1909) In English: Jung, C. G. (1961). The significance of the father in the destiny of the individual. In *Collected works* (Vol. 4, pp. 299–323). Princeton University Press.
- Jung, C. G. (1981). Symbole der Wandlung. In *Gesammelte Werke* (Vol. 5). Walter-Verlag. (Original work published 1952) In English: Jung, C. G. (1956). Symbols of transformation. In *Collected works* (Vol. 5). Princeton University Press.
- Jung, C. G. (1981). Psychologische Typen. In *Gesammelte Werke* (Vol. 6). Walter-Verlag. (Original work published 1920) In English: Jung, C. G. (1971). Psychological types. In *Collected works* (Vol. 6). Princeton University Press.
- Jung, C. G. (1981). Zwei Schriften über Analytische Psychologie. In *Gesammelte Werke* (Vol. 7). Walter-Verlag. (Original work published 1916). In English: Jung, C. G. (1966). Two essays on analytical psychology. In *Collected works* (Vol. 7). Princeton University Press.
- Jung, C. G. (1985). Die Archetypen und das kollektive Unbewußte. In *Gesammelte Werke* (Vol. 9/1). Walter-Verlag. (Original work published 1954) In English: Jung, C. G. (1968). The archetypes and the collective unconscious. In *Collected works* (Vol. 9/1). Princeton University Press.
- Jung, C. G. (1983). Psychologie und Religion. In *Gesammelte Werke* (Vol. 11, pp. 1–117). Walter-Verlag. (Original work published 1940) In English: Jung, C. G. (1958). Psychology and Western religion. In *Collected works* (Vol. 11, pp. 3–105). Princeton University Press.
- Jung, C. G. (1984). Psychologie und Dichtung. In *Gesammelte Werke* (Vol. 15, pp. 97–120). Walter-Verlag. (Original work published 1930) In English: Jung, C. G. (1966). Psychology and literature. In *Collected works* (Vol. 15, pp. 84–105). Princeton University Press.

- Jung, C. G. (1985). Analytische Psychologie und Erziehung. In *Gesammelte Werke* (Vol. 17, pp. 77–153). Walter-Verlag. (Original work published 1926) In English: Jung, C. G. (1954). Analytical psychology and education. In *Collected works* (Vol. 17, pp. 63–132). Princeton University Press.
- Jung, C. G. (1981). Über Grundlagen der Analytischen Psychologie (Tavistock Lectures). In *Gesammelte Werke* (Vol. 18, pp. 13–198). Walter-Verlag. (Original work published 1935) In English: Jung, C. G. (1968). The Tavistock Lectures: On the theory and practice of analytical psychology. In *Collected works* (Vol. 18, pp. 5–182). Princeton University Press.
- Jung, C. G. (1959, October 22). Interview with John Freeman [Television broadcast]. BBC. *Face to Face*. <https://iaap.org/video/face-to-face-carl-gustav-jung-1959>
- Kardaun, M. (2010). Depth psychological literary criticism: Some methodological questions. In F. Pereira (Ed.), *Proceedings of the Twenty-Sixth International Conference on Literature and Psychoanalysis* (pp. 79–84). Instituto Superior de Psicologia Aplicada.
- Kardaun, M. (2015). Review of Jung and the question of science by R. A. Jones (Ed.). *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, 29(1), 108–111. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02698595.2015.1027725>
- Kerényi, K. (2003). *Die Mythologie der Griechen: Die Götter- und Menschheitsgeschichten*. Deutscher Taschenbuch Verlag. (Original work published 1966)
- Kerényi, K. (2002). *Die Mythologie der Griechen: Die Heroen-Geschichten*. Deutscher Taschenbuch Verlag. (Original work published 1960)
- Kirk, G. S. (1990). *The nature of Greek myths*. Penguin. (Original work published 1974)
- Rijk, L. M. de. (2008). *Religie, normen, waarden: Een kritische blik op een maatschappelijk debat*. Bert Bakker. (Original work published 2006)
- Rijk, L. M. de. (2010). *Geloven en weten: Pleidooi voor een sober atheïsme*. Bert Bakker.
- Schönau, W. (1991). Literatuur en onttovering. In R. T. Segers (Ed.), *Visies op cultuur en literatuur: Opstellen naar aanleiding van het werk van J.J.A. Mooij* (pp. 203–209). Rodopi.
- Tolkien, J. R. R. (2006). Beowulf: The monsters and the critics. In C. Tolkien (Ed.), *The monsters and the critics and other essays* (pp. 5–48). HarperCollins. (Original work published 1936)
- Van Schaik, C., & Michel, K. (2020). *De waarheid over Eva: Hoe de ongelijkheid tussen vrouwen en mannen ontstond*. Balans.
- Waal, F. de. (2022). *Different: Gender through the eyes of a primatologist*. W. W. Norton & Company.
- Welling, W. (Ed.). (2012). *Goddelijk en griezelig—het geheim van de slang*. KIT Publishers.
- Welling, W. (2024). Het andere goud: Jung, beeldende kunst en alchemie. In K. Laan, H. Vlug, & T. Willemstijn (Eds.), *Jung en de elementen, Jaarboek 39 van de C.G. Jung Vereniging Nederland* (pp. 109–162). KIT Publishers.